

Ghana's Transition Pathways to Sustainability: A CLEWS-Based Study

Felix Amankwah Diawuo,
Samuel Akowuah Okyereh,
Emmanuel Asuamah Yeboah,
Mathew Anabadongo Atinsia,
Mamud Musah

University of Energy and Natural Resources, Sunyani, Ghana

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Executive Summary

Ghana faces significant energy sector challenges, including frequent power outages, rising sector debt, and 30% energy consumption losses. A Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWS) based study was conducted to assess the impacts of demand-side management (DSM) and renewable energy deployment on generation capacity investment, land use, and water demand from 2020 to 2070.

Two scenarios were analysed in this study. The first, Demand-Side Management (DSM), aimed at reducing the annual energy demand growth rate by 5% through strategies such as mandatory energy audits, and others. The second scenario focused on decarbonization through renewable energy integration (DE-RE), transitioning the power sector from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources, particularly solar and wind.

Results showed significant reductions in electricity generation costs and investments, increased reliance on local energy resources, and decreased water use for thermal cooling, though agricultural water demand rose. Land use for biodiesel production also increased.

These findings indicate that DSM strategies can effectively reduce energy demand and costs. It is recommended to revitalize the Renewable Energy Act and create a conducive environment for energy sector investments, alongside promoting afforestation in built-up areas. Finally, integrated CLEWS-based strategies can significantly enhance Ghana's sustainable development by improving energy efficiency and resource optimization.

- **Keywords:** Integrated Systems Analysis, Energy Modelling, Nexus Approach, CLEWs, OSeMOSYS

1 Introduction

Ghana, a nation of 33 million inhabitants within a 238,538 km² territory, aspires towards a sustainable future (AUDA NEPAD, 2023). However, achieving this goal necessitates navigating a complex landscape of interconnected challenges. The CLEWS framework provides a valuable lens to assess Ghana's progress and vulnerabilities across these critical dimensions.

This modelling work investigates potential pathways for Ghana's transition towards sustainability. The nation's current installed electricity capacity of 5.5 GW relies heavily on thermal sources (61%), with a concerning dependence on fossil fuels. This imbalance translates into incessant power outages, stemming from inadequate supply capacity and fuel shortages (Energy Commission, 2024). While hydropower contributes 38% to the energy mix, other renewables hold a mere 1% share. The World Bank estimates that in 2007 alone, such outages resulted in a staggering 1.8% GDP loss. A 2014 study by ISSER reiterates the economic burden, highlighting a US\$680 million loss, equivalent to roughly 2% of GDP (World Bank, 2022). Furthermore, the energy sector struggles with substantial debt, hindering further investment in essential infrastructure.

Compounding these challenges, a report by the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) indicates a 30% wastage in residential electricity consumption due to inefficient appliances (IRENA, 2023). This inefficiency underscores the urgency for not only expanding generation capacity but also promoting responsible consumption practices.

In this report, we utilised the CLEWS framework to explore some of Ghana's current sustainability pathways. By evaluating existing policies and programs, we aim to develop feasible transition pathway scenarios. These scenarios will prioritize actionable recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders, ultimately accelerating Ghana's progress on its chosen path towards a sustainable future.

1.1 Objectives

Firstly, it was to explore sustainability transition through demand-side management and increase in Renewables by utilising the CLEWS framework to assess potential impacts across the nexus.

Secondly, it was to develop a data-driven model for Ghana's transition towards a sustainable future, prioritising the most impactful interventions across the CLEWS framework.

2 Methodology

This work was conducted using the Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) application whilst applying the CLEWS framework for Ghana. OSeMOSYS is an open-source tool designed for long-term energy planning and integrated resource management, allowing the simulation of interactions between energy, land, water, and climate systems (KTH-dESA, 2023). The reference CLEWs diagram for the model is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 Simplified Reference CLEWS diagram

2.1 Data Sources

To ensure a robust analysis, data for this study was meticulously collected from various authoritative sources. National statistics were obtained from Statista. Energy data, including production and consumption figures, came from the Ministry of Energy Ghana, the Ghana Energy Commission, and the International Energy Agency (IEA). Agricultural data on land use and productivity was compiled from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the Ministry

of Food and Agriculture. Water availability and usage information was sourced from the Volta River Authority and the Ghana Water Company.

2.2 Assumptions

Key assumptions underpinning the model include:

- Population Growth: Based on projections from GSS.
- Economic Growth: Assumed GDP growth rates derived from historical trends and national targets.
- Energy Prices: Projected to follow international market trends, adjusted for local conditions.
- Technological Advancement: Assumes gradual improvements in energy efficiency and renewable technologies.
- Policy Environment: Assumes current policies remain with considerations for announced future initiatives.

2.3 Scenarios and Sensitivity Analysis

The following scenarios shown in Table 1 explore different pathways for the future. By analysing these scenarios, we can assess the effectiveness of different approaches in addressing Ghana's sustainability challenges within the CLEWS framework.

Table 1 Scenarios Description

SCENARIO		Description
1	Baseline	This scenario represents a continuation of current trends and existing policies. It serves as a baseline to compare the impact of potential interventions.
2	Demand Side Management (DSM)	This scenario prioritises efficiency by aiming for a 5% annual reduction in energy demand growth. It explores the impact of measures like mandatory energy audits and appliance standards.
3	Decarbonization based on renewable energy (DE_RE)	This scenario focuses on decarbonising the power sector by shifting towards renewable energy sources like solar and wind. This will illuminate the feasibility and consequences of a significant renewable energy push.

3 Results

3.1 Power Generation

The power generation in both scenarios can be seen in Figure 2. The results indicate a significant reduction in the electricity demand indicating a reduction in investment and cost of electricity generation. Also, the results show a tendency for the high transition towards the use of endogenous resources for electricity, evident in the high rise in biomass resources in scenario 2. This use of these endogenous resources leads to energy security, energy independence and support for local resources.

Figure 2: Power generation results showing the baseline scenario, scenario 1 and scenario 2.

3.2 Water Demand

The results for the water demand can be seen in Figure 3. The results indicate a reduction in water demand in both scenarios. Again, it can be seen in scenario 2 that there is an increase in water demand for agriculture due to the reduction in biofuel production.

Figure 3: Water demand-supply for the baseline scenario, scenario 1 and scenario 2.

3.3 Area by Land Cover

The results for the area by land cover can be seen in Figure 4. Both scenario 1 and scenario 2 show a significant increase in agricultural land use for biofuel production for power generation.

Figure 4: Area by land cover for the baseline scenario, scenario 1 and scenario

4 Discussion

4.1 Power Generation Analysis and Future Scenarios for Ghana

The baseline power generation model represents Ghana's electricity production without any new interventions or scenarios. It primarily consists of hydro, thermal, and nuclear power plants and these sources collectively meet the current and projected energy demands.

When demand-side management (DSM) interventions are introduced, there is a noticeable decline in the projected energy demand profile from 2020 to 2070. This reduction in demand delays the need for new power plant investments or lowers the required investment levels. DSM is considered an effective and easily implemented strategy to decrease energy consumption. By reducing overall energy demand, DSM also contributes to lower CO₂ emissions, thus enhancing sustainability. There is a significant reduction in water use for cooling thermal plants and more available for agricultural purposes

Scenario 2 (De-RE) explored the gradual integration of renewable energy sources to achieve a 95% share of Ghana's total power generation mix. As illustrated in the figure...., biomass is projected to constitute a significant portion of the power generation. This shift would necessitate an expansion of agricultural land for biofuel production. Consequently, there is a critical need to adopt measures such as utilizing deforested lands or investing in climate-smart agriculture to mitigate competition between land for food and land for fuel.

Implementing these strategies will significantly reduce investment and operational costs for electricity generation while enhancing Ghana's energy security through the use of local, renewable resources. This approach also promotes long-term environmental sustainability by lowering natural resource utilization and CO₂ emissions, allowing Ghana to effectively manage future energy demands and reduce reliance on imported fuels.

4.2 Policy insights

Revitalize the RE Act to promote adopting and integrating renewable energy sources. This involves updating and enforcing legislation to reflect current technological advancements and

market conditions, ensuring supportive policies and incentives are in place to encourage public and private sector participation.

Creating a conducive environment for private-sector investment is essential for accelerating sustainable infrastructure development and energy projects. This can be achieved by streamlining regulatory processes, offering financial incentives, and ensuring policy stability. A supportive investment climate attracts private capital, fosters innovation, and accelerates the implementation of green technologies, leading to economic growth and sustainable development.

5 Conclusion

The study concludes that integrating advanced energy systems and renewable energy sources significantly reduces electricity generation's investment and operational costs. By optimising energy production processes, the financial burden on both providers and consumers can be substantially alleviated. This reduction in costs not only makes energy more affordable but also stimulates further investments in sustainable energy infrastructure, fostering economic growth and sustainability.

DSM strategies are highlighted as low-hanging fruits that can readily reduce energy consumption and associated investment costs. Implementing DSM strategies offers immediate benefits in terms of cost savings and improved system efficiency.

The study also finds that high penetration of RE enhances energy security by utilizing endogenous resources, thus reducing dependence on imported fuels and mitigating risks associated with supply disruptions. Additionally, DSM strategies lead to less water demand for cooling thermal power plants, as overall energy consumption is reduced and more efficient, less water-intensive renewable energy sources are utilised.

5.1 Future studies

- Develop a more detailed CLEWS model tailored explicitly for the Volta and Tana River basins to analyse and optimise resource use and sustainability.
- Investigate the integration of advanced battery storage technologies within energy systems in increasing renewables in the energy mix and its impacts on emissions and climate.
- Focus on strategic planning and development of infrastructure that supports sustainable growth, considering future demands and potential challenges such as urbanisation and population growth.
- Research and implement strategies for mitigating the impacts of climate change, focusing on reducing greenhouse gas emissions and enhancing adaptive capacities.
- Establish a data observatory dedicated to collecting, analysing, and disseminating Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems data to support informed decision-making and policy development.

6 References

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